

Measurement of Viscosity Coefficients of some Solutes in Dimethylformamide + Ethyl methyl ketone Mixtures at 25°

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Viscosities of some solutes have been measured in dimethylformamide (DMF), ethyl methyl ketone (EMK) and DMF+EMK mixtures at 25°. The viscosity data has been analysed by the Jones-Dole equation for electrolytes to evaluate A and B coefficients of viscosity. A and B coefficients for all the electrolytes are positive and B -coefficients have been split up into the contribution due to individual ions (B_{\pm} values). An examination of B_{\pm} coefficients as a function of solvent composition indicates that B_{+} and B_{-} values of tetraalkylammonium cations and anions respectively remain almost constant, whereas B_{+} values for Na^{+} and K^{+} first increase, show a maximum and then decrease with the addition of EMK content in the DMF+EMK solvent mixtures. This shows that there is no preferential solvation for tetraalkylammonium ions but Na^{+} and K^{+} ions exhibit preferential solvation in DMF+EMK mixtures.

In continuation with our previous work in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) + dioxane¹, acetonitrile (AN)+DMSO^{2,3} on preferential solvation behaviour of ions using conductance and viscosity measurements, the present communication reports the viscosity data for tetrabutylammoniumtetraphenylborate (Bu_4NBPh_4), tetrabutylammoniumiodide (Bu_4NI), sodiumtetraphenylborate (NaBPh_4), sodium iodide (NaI) and potassium iodide (KI) in dimethylformamide (DMF), ethyl methyl ketone (EMK) and DMF+EMK mixtures at 25°.

Results and Discussion

Viscosities of Bu_4NBPh_4 , Bu_4NI , NaBPh_4 , NaI and KI have been measured over concentration range $(15-115) \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} in DMF, EMK and DMF+EMK mixtures containing 0.938, 0.685, 0.493, 0.309, 0.085 mole fraction of DMF at 25°. Since KI was not found soluble in pure EMK, hence studies have not been carried out in 0.915 and 1.0 mole fraction of EMK.

Dielectric constant, viscosity and density data of solvent mixtures are given in Fig 1 and Table 1. The experimentally determined density and viscosity values of solvent mixtures of DMF, EMK and DMF+EMK are in close agreement with the literature values⁴. Fig. 1 gives the linear plots of density and viscosity as a function of mole fraction of DMF in DMF+EMK systems showing the ideal behaviour of solvent systems. Hence it can be said that there is no intermolecular interaction among the molecules of EMK and DMF.

The entire viscosity data have been analysed by the Jones-Dole⁵ equation,

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + AC\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

The viscosity A and B coefficients of equation (1) have been evaluated from the linear plots (Fig. 2) of $(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} by least-square method.

The calculated A and B coefficients of the electrolytes are reported in Table 2. The A coefficients are positive and small indicating that their contribution to absolute viscosity is small. The B values are large and positive which is a common feature in most non-aqueous solvents^{1,2,6-8}. The accuracy of the present measurements has been checked by comparing the B values reported in the literature for some electrolytes in DMF^{6,8} only. The reported B values for Bu_4NBPh_4 , Bu_4NI , NaBPh_4 , NaI and KI in DMF are respectively 1.92, 1.20, 1.85, 1.12 and 1.12 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 25°, which are in fairly good agreement with the present values of 1.95 ± 0.03 , 1.19 ± 0.03 , 1.85 ± 0.03 , 1.12 ± 0.02 and $1.09 \pm 0.03 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Also, the B coefficient of Bu_4NBPh_4 in EMK ($2.04 \pm 0.03 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) is in good agreement with the reported value ($2.02 \pm 0.06 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)⁹.

Fig. 1. Plots of d and η of pure solvent mixture vs mole fraction of DMF: (○) viscosity η_0 and (Δ) density d .

TABLE 1—DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS (*D*)* OF DMF, EMK AND DMF+EMK MIXTURES AT 25°

<i>X</i> _{DMF}	<i>D</i>
0.000	18.01
0.085	19.63
0.309	23.19
0.493	26.48
0.685	30.11
0.938	35.76
1.000	36.71

*Ref. 4.

Fig. 2 Plots of $(\eta - \eta_0)/\eta_0\sqrt{c}$ vs \sqrt{c} for some salts in 0.685 mole fraction of DMF: (●) Bu_4NI , (Δ) KI , (■) NaI , (▲) $NaBPh_4$ and (○) Bu_4NBPh_4 .

Ionic B_{\pm} coefficients in DMF, EMK and DMF+EMK mixtures: Since there is no corresponding quantity in viscosity as transference number in conductance, hence the separation of the observed B coefficients of the electrolytes has been an arbitrary process. Several methods have been suggested in the literature for the calculation of ionic B_+ and B_- coefficients from the total B coefficients of the

electrolytes. One of the recently proposed arbitrary methods^{8, 9, 10} consists of following equations,

$$\frac{B_{Ph_4B^-}}{B_{Bu_4N^+}} = \left(\frac{5.35}{5.00}\right)^3 \quad (2)$$

and

$$B_{Bu_4NBPh_4} = B_{Bu_4N^+} + B_{Ph_4B^-} \quad (3)$$

Using equations (2) and (3), the B coefficients of Bu_4NBPh_4 in DMF and EMK mixtures from Table 2 have been resolved into the contribution of $B_{Bu_4N^+}$ and $B_{Ph_4B^-}$ values. From these B_{\pm} values and B values of all other electrolytes (Table 2), ionic B_{\pm} coefficient values for other ions have been calculated (Table 3). The B_{\pm} values of the ions agree well with the literature values in DMF⁹ and EMK⁹. The self-consistency of the viscosity data in the present investigation has been checked by comparing the B values of NaI and DMF and DMF+EMK mixtures from Table 2 with the corresponding B values obtained by adding B_{Na^+} calculated from $NaBPh_4$ and B_{I^-} calculated from Bu_4NI from Table 3. The agreement between these two sets of B_{NaI} values is fairly good (with an average uncertainty of ± 0.03 units).

Solvation behaviour of ions: In a binary solvent mixture, non-linear variation of B_{\pm} value of ion as a function of solvent composition shows the preferential solvation of that particular ion. It is evident (Table 3) that B_+ value for tetrabutylammonium (Bu_4N^+) ion remains almost constant as one moves from pure DMF to pure EMK. The B_- values for anions Ph_4B^- and I^- also do not change with the addition of EMK over the whole composition range of solvent mixture. The B_+ value for alkali metal Na^+ and K^+ ions increases with the increase of EMK content, reaches maximum and then decreases.

It is observed from literature studies that tetraalkylammonium cations and anions generally show no variation in B_{\pm} values in dipolar aprotic solvent systems^{2, 6, 11}. The alkali metal cations show non-linear or linear variation in B_{\pm} values as a function of composition and nature of solvent mixture^{2, 3, 11}.

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY A ($dm^3 mol^{-1}$)^{1/2} AND B ($dm^3 mol^{-1}$) COEFFICIENTS OF SOME SALTS IN DMF, EMK AND DMF + EMK MIXTURES AT 25°

Salt	100		0.938		0.685		0.493		0.309		0.085		EMK	
	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>
Bu_4NBPh_4	2.09	1.95	1.23	1.90	2.50	1.94	4.82	1.91	3.79	1.96	2.361	1.96	4.21	2.04
		(1.92) ^a												(2.02) ^c
Bu_4NI	3.30	1.19	3.19	1.15	1.14	1.16	1.19	1.16	4.96	1.15	3.55	1.14	3.95	1.16
		(1.20) ^b												
$NaBPh_4$	2.55	1.85	1.05	1.90	3.45	1.88	2.35	1.90	3.79	1.80	2.21	1.76	4.78	1.88
		(1.85) ^b												
NaI	2.85	1.10	1.92	1.11	3.61	1.13	2.63	1.18	3.78	1.04	2.53	1.01	3.06	0.99
		(1.12) ^b												
KI	2.05	1.09	2.36	1.08	1.34	1.11	1.95	1.16	2.04	1.07	—	—	—	—
		(1.12) ^b												

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 6. ^cRef. 9.

TABLE 3—IONIC B_{\pm} COEFFICIENTS ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) FOR SOME IONS IN DMF, EMK AND DMF+EMK MIXTURES AT 25°

Ion	B_{\pm} ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)						
	DMF	0.938	0.685	0.493	0.309	0.085	EMK
Bu_4N^+	0.88 (0.86) ^a	0.86	0.87	0.86	0.88	0.88	0.92
Na^+	0.79	0.82	0.84	0.88	0.77	0.75	0.75
K^+	0.78 (0.77) ^b	0.79	0.82	0.86	0.80	—	—
Ph_4B^-	1.07 (1.06) ^a	1.04	1.07	1.05	1.08	1.08	1.12
I^-	0.31	0.29	0.29	0.30	0.27	0.26	0.24

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 6.

The B_{\pm} values of 0.88, 1.07 and 0.78 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for Bu_4N^+ , Ph_4B^- and K^+ ions respectively, in DMF from the present study, are in close agreement with the values of 0.86, 1.06 and 0.77 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ as reported in literature^{6,8}. It is clear from Table 3 that B_{\pm} values for Bu_4N^+ , Ph_4B^- and I^- ions do not show significant change while going from DMF to EMK; for example, in case of Bu_4N^+ ion, B_{\pm} values are 0.88, 0.86, 0.87, 0.86, 0.88, 0.88 and 0.92 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ which are practically constant. The same is true for Ph_4B^- and I^- ions. This indicates that Bu_4N^+ , Ph_4B^- and I^- ions show no preferential solvation in DMF+EMK mixtures. On the other hand, the B_{\pm} values for Na^+ ion are 0.79, 0.82, 0.84, 0.88, 0.77, 0.75 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ and for K^+ ion are 0.78, 0.79, 0.82, 0.86 and 0.80 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ with a maximum at 0.493 mole fraction of DMF. This non-linear variation indicates preferential solvation of both Na^+ and K^+ ions in this solvent system.

The observed conclusion regarding variation of B_{\pm} values for Bu_4N^+ , Ph_4B^- , I^- , Na^+ and K^+ are in complete agreement with the results reported in literature for other solvent systems like DMSO+AN^{2,3} and DMSO+acetone⁷.

Experimental

DMF and EMK were purified by the methods reported in literature and purity of the solvents was checked⁴. The binary mixtures of these solvents containing 1.00, 0.938, 0.685, 0.493, 0.309, 0.085 and zero mole fraction of DMF were prepared (by weight) and the viscosities of these solvent mixtures as well as of the electrolyte solutions were measured at (25.00 ± 0.01°) with a Ubbelohde suspended bulb level viscometer having flow time of 520 s for water. The electrolytes used were prepared and purified as reported earlier^{1,2}. The overall accuracy of the viscosity measurements was ± 0.1%.

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